

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15062279>

A MODERN APPROACH TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN STATE AND NON-STATE EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

R.K.Ollaberganova

Joint Belarusian-Uzbek intersectoral institute of Applied Technical
Qualifications in Tashkent city

***Annotation.** The article reveals the content of the concept of "approach to teaching" in relation to the methodology of teaching foreign languages; analyzes the modern characteristics of this category of teaching communication in a foreign language; studies both the most frequently used approaches and general approaches used in related disciplines in the new conditions of traditional, distance and blended teaching of English.*

***Keywords:** approach to teaching, communicative, innovative communicative, holistic/comprehensive, integrated, individual, competence-based, differentiated, activity-based, structural-functional.*

Introduction. In today's world, where globalization plays a key role, knowledge of foreign languages is becoming increasingly important for a successful career and personal development. Students who want to master a foreign language have access to various teaching methods and technologies that make the learning process more fun, effective, and accessible.

The relevance of this study is due to the progressive development of the field of studying foreign languages, the adaptability of teaching methods, and the development of international communication. In many ways, this is facilitated by the Internet and social networks, which allow users to communicate with each other despite the distance

and differences in cultural characteristics. Now, more than ever, modern methods and technologies for teaching foreign languages are relevant, as the demand for training is increasing. Many young specialists can build a career abroad, go to live or study in another country. New teaching methods will allow people to study a new language more deeply and get acquainted with another culture.

Analysis of literature on the topic. The term "approach to teaching" is a basic concept of foreign language teaching methods, determining the choice of methods, techniques, and technologies for teaching a given subject [3]. Teaching methods, in turn, determine the tactical model of the educational process. There is no consensus among researchers regarding this term and its main characteristics. Let's look at the most famous of them. The following interpretations of this category are worth noting. M. V. Lyakhovitsky identifies four general approaches to teaching foreign languages, emphasizing psychological processes:

- 1) behaviorist approach;
- 2) inductive-conscious approach;
- 3) cognitive approach;

4) integrated approach [6]. I. A. Zimnyaya's understanding of the term "approach to learning" highlights the position of the learning object as the dominant: language approach, speech approach, speech activity approach, or communicative activity approach) [4].

The purpose of this article is to analyze various interpretations of this category and review the most relevant approaches for the modern period of teaching foreign languages. The following approaches are recognized as relevant and generally accepted for the methodology of teaching foreign languages: personality-oriented, communicative, competence-based, intercultural, and axiological.

The personality-oriented approach to teaching foreign languages has changed the main emphasis from the teacher's personality to the development of the secondary linguistic personality of the student, capable of self-development, self-knowledge, and self-realization based on the formation of his unique individuality and the choice of his

own learning path. Nevertheless, the problem of personalization of the educational process still remains open. Teachers are recommended to create a psychologically comfortable atmosphere that promotes the development of creative and intellectual abilities of students and strengthens their self-confidence. It is believed that this creates the prerequisites for greater learning effectiveness and will allow taking into account the subjective experience of the student and his individual style of cognitive activity, which will help intercultural dialogue and interpersonal contacts [7].

The formation of a secondary linguistic personality is transferred by some researchers to the category of the main goals of teaching a foreign language (I.I. Khaleeva). The individual approach, which highlights the pedagogical principle of an individual learning trajectory as a dominant, according to which the pedagogical influence on each child is based on knowledge of his personality and living conditions, echoes the above approach. It, like the first approach, points to the need for personalization of the educational process.

Some scientists distinguish the well-known differentiated approach to teaching, which consists of revealing the individuality of the student and then selecting the most favorable conditions for his development through the proposed differentiated forms of teaching. This implies revealing the individuality of the student and choosing the most favorable conditions for his development through the proposed differentiated forms of teaching. The differentiated approach takes into account the differences between groups of students according to their social, age, educational, and professional orientation. The approaches considered above are based on fairly similar categories of personalization and individualization of the educational process and the resulting differentiation of forms of teaching.

At present, the leading role is undoubtedly played by the communicative approach. The main idea of this approach is to assume the practical application of the language being studied in specific situations of interpersonal and intercultural communication and not just memorization of language forms and grammar rules. The task is to form practical skills and communication abilities in educational situations.

Hence, one of the main tasks of teaching foreign languages at the present stage is the formation and teaching of practical skills and educational abilities within the framework of interpersonal and intercultural communication.

The innovative and communicative approach to learning has become important at present. Here it is appropriate to distinguish two main types: technological (aimed at the formation of practical skills and abilities) and search (cognitive), which correspond to the reproductive and problematic orientation of the educational process.

The most widespread approach in recent times is the competence-based approach, which provides for the focus of the pedagogical process on the formation of students' universal, professional, general subject, and general cultural competencies in the process of teaching a foreign language. It is believed that competence is formed as a consequence of the independent cognitive activity of the student and his self-development [8].

The intercultural approach to teaching a foreign language sets the dominant task of introducing students to the cultural traditions and customs of the countries of the language being studied, as well as familiarizing them with linguistic and cultural realities and background knowledge. It is expected that this will facilitate adequate and effective communication with native speakers of the language being studied.

No less important is the axiological approach, or more precisely, the philosophical and pedagogical direction, based on the resources for improving the education system, namely, on the axiological principles and provisions traditional for the Russian mentality, which allow maintaining ideological and systemic values. Most researchers and practicing teachers consider the use of the axiological approach to be one of the possibilities for solving the problem of humanizing education. It is generally recognized that an individual system of value social guidelines is the basis for the formation of an independent, creative personality of a student, capable of solving communicative problems outside the framework of educational situations by means of the studied language. It is obvious that the system of ideals and values accepted in society helps to form a developed linguistic personality, including its ability for

independent critical thinking. The system of life values determines morality and communicative behavior of students. The personality becomes an object of purposeful education and interaction with the social environment and civilization as a whole.

In addition to the main five approaches discussed above, some other equally important provisions for teaching foreign languages should be taken into account. Undoubtedly, the holistic approach to teaching deserves attention, which emphasizes the teacher's orientation regarding the choice of teaching methods, which involves the Implementation of the main links of educational activity: a) the organization and implementation of educational and cognitive activity; b) stimulation and motivation of educational work; c) control and self-control of the effectiveness of training [2].

Another important traditional learning strategy is an integrated approach to learning and education. Planning, organization and correlation of pedagogical technologies and educational processes are important here. The teacher designs and takes into account various aspects and aspects of speech activity, as well as situational features of communication in the external environment. The integrated approach echoes the systemic one. It is generally recognized that all the conditions and components of the pedagogical process (educational institutions of different levels and directions) and the constants of educational interaction (goals, objectives, content, methods, technologies and techniques) need to be brought into interrelation and interaction. It is necessary to coordinate the main parameters and system-forming components of the educational process. Unlike the system, the complex is always limited to certain communication situations and the framework of etiquette of behavior, while the system must take into account all possible connections at both the communicative and educational levels, while remaining autonomous. An integrated approach to teaching and upbringing by means of a foreign language is expressed in the establishment of patterns and relationships between all facets of the formation of students' citizenship and the development of linguistic personality. The educational process should have a single target guide, while eliminating all possible contradictions.

An integrative approach to learning is based on the principle of restoring the natural integrity of the cognitive process by establishing connections and relationships between artificially separated components of the pedagogical process. This approach is used in the formation of the content of teaching and educational technologies, in the design of the process of preparing and conducting forms of organization of educational activities (lesson, lecture, seminar), in the formation of individual pedagogical systems. The integrative principle expands the area of action of the teacher (including the researcher). It provides for the connection of artificially, mechanically separated academic subjects, pedagogical functions, constituent substructures and their components. Integration allows you to reunite certain elements both vertically (through interdisciplinary and managerial connections) and horizontally (through intrasubject, technological connections). With the help of an integrative approach, it is possible to support the historically established naturalness of the learning process, contribute to achieving its naturalness and rapprochement with life.

The generally accepted multi-level approach to teaching retains its importance, providing for a different level of complexity of the material being studied, ensuring its accessibility to each student. It is carried out taking into account the subjective experience of students, using the indicative foundations of mental actions [9].

The technologized approach to teaching foreign languages is built as a technological, conveyor process with clearly fixed, detailed expected results. Special attention is paid to setting pedagogical goals. It is believed that goals should be formulated as the expected results of students' activities in the form of specific skills. In modern teaching methods, this approach has been transformed and is based on the use of modern technical teaching tools (computers, tablets, smartphones and other digital devices). It echoes the innovative information approach, which provides for remote support of the educational process using various electronic platforms, servers and educational information environments.

The structural and functional approach to teaching foreign languages is based on the communicative function of the language and provides for maximum immersion in

language activities. The purpose of this approach is to create an educational foreign language environment in which students could function: namely, "read, communicate, participate in role-playing games, express their thoughts, draw conclusions – that is, choose a structure for their speech act in accordance with the function performed" [5].

The activity-based approach to learning focuses on the main types of speech activity: listening, reading, speaking and writing. It is assumed that the presence of all these types in the lesson will contribute to the education and development of the student's linguistic personality. This strategy is based on the idea of a reasonable combination of speech activity in a foreign language and the corresponding cognitive, mental activity, as well as on the activity-mediated development of interpersonal relations, on their unity in internal and external manifestation. The predominance of one or another type of speech activity in the educational process of learning a foreign language is possible, but based on the complex nature of the category "Foreign language lesson". It is generally recognized that the teacher should strive to use all types of speech activity in the lesson, choosing appropriate communication situations.

Conclusion, The heuristic (search) approach reorganizes traditional learning with the help of productive types of speech and creative educational and cognitive activities, it determines the choice of learning models based on the new experience of students. At the same time, the emphasis shifts to the reflective activity of students, which determines both the procedural and the substantive side of learning. A generalized model within the framework of the search approach is the model of teaching creative search: from problem formulation to making assumptions, hypotheses, then to their verification and reflection on the results obtained and the process of cognition. A common characteristic is a change in the position of the student, his perception of the educational process as an active participant in it – a participant in heuristic research, games and discussions. This approach is based on the same postulates as the cognitive one.

The cognitive approach is based on taking into account the patterns of the cognitive process in mastering a foreign language and considers the features of the

"mental (intellectual-emotional) activity of students, in whom the development of a new linguistic system is accomplished through the interaction of internal and external factors" [10]. The main goal here is to educate students in the desire to independently master new experiences and acquire new knowledge on the subject. Cognitive teaching of foreign languages is based on the principles of cognitive psychology and structural applied linguistics.

Based on the above approaches to teaching foreign languages, various practical learning models are being formed. The optimization of the educational process with the skillful alternation and combination of the entire system of approaches is based mainly on extensive forms of education, the criterion of effectiveness of which is the degree of mastery by students of a certain set of knowledge offered by the teacher and contained in textbooks and teaching aids.

References:

1. Averchenko, I. V. Modern approaches to teaching foreign languages and their integrative essence / I. V. Averchenko, L. V. Khvedchenya. – Minsk: BSU, 2009. – Text : electronic // Electronic library of BSU. – URL: <https://elib.bsu.by/handle/123456789/148105> (date of application: 02/27/2023). – Access mode: for authorization. users.
2. Babansky, Y.K. Selected pedagogical works / Comp. M.Y.Babansky. – Moscow: Pedagogy, 1989. – 560 p.
3. Bim, I.L. Theory and practice of teaching German in secondary school. Problems and prospects / I. L. Bim. – Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 1988. – 255 p.
4. Zimnaya, I. A. Psychological aspects of learning to speak a foreign language : A book for a teacher / I. A. Zimnaya. – 2nd ed. – Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 1985. – 160 p.
5. Antonenko, T. I. A structural and functional approach to teaching practical grammar of a foreign language in higher education and school / T. I. Antonenko, E. G.

Vvlitskaya, A.V. Korzo // Actual problems of teaching foreign languages in higher education of the Republic of Belarus - 2014 : collection of scientific articles : [collection of materials of the III Republican Scientific Internet Conference; Mogilev, October 25 – December 25, 2014 / edited by E. E. Ivanov. Mogilev : Kuleshov Moscow State University, 2015. pp. 66-71.

6. Lyakhovitsky M. V. Methods of teaching foreign languages: a textbook for philologists. special universities / M. V. Lyakhovitsky. – Moscow: Higher School, 1981. – 159 p.

7. Milrud, R. P. Methods of teaching English. English Teaching Methodology : a textbook for universities / R. P. Milrud. – 2nd ed. – Moscow : Bustard, 2007. – 257 p.

8. Nazmutdinov, V. Ya. Competence approach in education / V. Ya. Nazmutdinov, G. R. Yusupova // Scientific notes of the Kazan State Academy of Veterinary Medicine named after N. E. Bauman. – 2013. – Volume 213. – Issue 1. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/kompetentnostnyy-podhod-v-obuchenii> (date of application: 12.01.2023).

9. Sitchenko, A. L. Methods of teaching literature: an educational and methodical manual / A. L. Sitchenko, V. V. Gladyshev. – Moscow: FLINT, 2014. – 158 p. – Text : electronic // Lan : electronic library system. – URL: <https://e.lanbook.com/book/48278> (date of application: 02/13/2023). – Access mode: for authorization. users.

10. Tretyakova, G. V. Cognitive approach in teaching a foreign language as a motivational tool for students / G. V. Tretyakova // Communication and teaching /Communication and Teaching. – SERVICE plus SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL. – 2021. – № 15(2). – Pp. 124-132. – Text : electronic // Lan : electronic library system. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/kognitivnyy-podhod-v-obuchenii-inostrannomu-yazyku-kak-motivatsionnyy-instrument-dlya-studentov> (date of access: 02/27/2023). – Access mode: for authorization. users.